

Data management plan (DMP)

Privacy-Sensitive Conversations between Care Workers and Care Home Residents in a Residential Care Home

Caring Robots // Robotic Care

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0.0	04/12/2024	First version of the DMP – created for the initial publication of the synthetic data resulting from the project track.

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I General Information

<p>I.1 Administrative information</p>	<p>Project title: Caring Robots // Robotic Care</p> <p>Project track: Privacy-Sensitive Conversations between Care Workers and Care Home Residents in a Residential Care Home</p> <p>PI: Sabine Theresia Koeszegi, sabine.koeszegi@tuwien.ac.at, TU Wien, ROR: ror.org/04d836q62</p> <p>FWF grant information: Austrian Science Fund (FWF), #ConnectingMinds, ConnectingMinds-Project, CM 100-N</p> <p>DMP version: 1.0.0, [04.12.2024]</p>
<p>I.2 Data management responsibilities and resources</p>	<p>Person responsible for data management and DMP: Reinhard Grabler, reinhard.grabler@tuwien.ac.at, TU Wien, ROR: ror.org/04d836q62</p> <p>Co-ordination of data management responsibilities across partners:</p> <p>Ralf Vetter, ralf.vetter@it-u.at (IT:U) and Evelyn Mayer-Haas, Evelyn.Mayer-Haas@caritas-wien.at (Caritas Wien)</p> <p>Resources costed in for RDM:</p> <p>There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR. No additional resources are needed for data management and storage.</p>

II Data Characteristics

<p>II.1 Data description and collection or reuse of existing data</p>	<p>Produced datasets:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="439 874 1733 1059"> <thead> <tr> <th>dataset ID</th> <th>title</th> <th>type</th> <th>format</th> <th>estimated volume</th> <th>contains sensitive data</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>P1</td> <td>Synthesized privacy-sensitive conversations</td> <td>Structured text</td> <td>jsonl</td> <td>100 MB</td> <td>no</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Methods and software used for data generation and reuse</p> <p>The initial original data (audio recordings and transcriptions) is collected in the project Caring Robots of TU Wien in cooperation with Caritas Wien. This project track aims to facilitate Large Language Models (LLM) to support documentation of care workers, with LLM-generated summaries of audio recordings of interactions between care workers and care home residents. The initial data are the LLM-generated transcriptions of those care interactions. The transcriptions are thoroughly reviewed, and sections containing privacy-sensitive information are identified and marked using qualitative data analysis software by experts. Subsequently, the accessible portions of the interviews are translated using an locally executed LLM. Another locally executed LLM is used to synthesize the conversation segments. This process involved generating similar, yet distinct and new, conversations that are not linked to the original data. The resulting dataset P1 (Synthesized privacy-sensitive conversations) will be split for machine learning applications.</p>	dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data	P1	Synthesized privacy-sensitive conversations	Structured text	jsonl	100 MB	no
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III Documentation and Data Quality

III.1 Metadata and documentation

Data organisation, metadata, and documentation:

The dataset P1 will be used for fine-tuning Large Language Models (LLMs). The community standard for documenting such datasets is exemplified by Hugging Face (huggingface.co), where metadata is typically provided in a README file at the dataset level. This metadata helps users of the platform to find and use the data set. It contains information such as subsets, splits, tags, language, size, license and the creators. The correct specification of this metadata allows the data to be displayed correctly in the Hugging Face interface. Furthermore, the README describes the published data in detail, including the data structure, data creation (including the annotation strategy) and what needs to be considered when using the data. The parameters specified in the README are based on datasets that fulfill similar tasks, such as [dair-ai/emotion](#) und [ai4privacy/pii-masking-400k](#).

The data will be managed in a way that the FAIR principles can be applied. This means that the data will be stored in secure, backed-up systems. They are collected and described in a structured way, e.g. with consistent naming conventions, and an indication of the data creation as described in the README.

Is the data machine-readable?

The files are provided in the data format “.jsonl,” the JSON Lines text format, also called newline-delimited JSON. Therefore, P1 (Synthesized privacy-sensitive conversations) will be machine readable (.jsonl). This format was selected because Hugging Face can automatically convert it to Parquet for display in the Dataset Viewer and for download. Parquet offers more efficient compression, reducing memory usage, which is advantageous for machine learning tasks. Meanwhile, the JSONL format remains human-readable, unlike the binary Parquet format, making it easier to track and recognize changes during versioning.

For publication at TU Wien Research Data Research Data, the files are all saved in the project root. Files will follow the naming convention **subset-split-language.jsonl**. An example file name is: **split-train-en.jsonl**. For language codes ISO 639 is used.

For the publication at Hugging Face (huggingface.co) it is usual that the data is stored in a “data” folder. The data structure will therefore be different, and the individual files will be organized in subfolders. Different languages in a split are stored in the same subfolder with the respective language code.

```
data/  
├─ subset/  
│   └─ split/  
│       └─ language.jsonl
```

III.2 Data quality control	<p>Data quality control:</p> <p>Data quality checks will be done. Data entry validation checks are performed as data is entered to ensure that it conforms to the defined rules (labels, annotations, etc). The data will be checked for logical errors and will be version controlled.</p>
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IV Data Storage, Sharing, and Long-Term Preservation

IV.1 Data storage and backup during the research process	<p>Storage and backup facilities:</p> <p>For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager in cooperation with the responsible representative of TU.it. The infrastructure of TU Wien will be used for this purpose.</p> <p>P1 (Synthesized privacy-sensitive conversations) will be stored on TUprouCloud: TUprouCloud is a sync&share service for projects provided by TU.it. Only authorized staff members and project partners will have access to the TUprouCloud folders. Deleted files can be recovered within 180 days by using the bin function.</p> <p>P1 (Synthesized privacy-sensitive conversations) will also be stored on MS SharePoint of TU Wien. External storage will be utilized through an established SharePoint folder accessible to all project members. SharePoint, integrated with Microsoft 365, facilitates seamless collaboration on shared documents, making it an ideal choice for this project.</p> <p>The data will be versioned using TUGitLab, TU Wien's institutional GitLab instance.</p> <p>Data security and protection of sensitive data:</p> <p>We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in this use case of the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.</p> <p>Access to data during research:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="436 1045 1646 1204"> <thead> <tr> <th>dataset ID</th> <th>selected project members</th> <th>all other project members</th> <th>the public</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>P1</td> <td>writing</td> <td>reading only</td> <td>reading only</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.</p>	dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public	P1	writing	reading only	reading only
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IV.2 Data sharing and long-term preservation

Data publication and access conditions:

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2024-12-04	TU Wien Research Data	10.70124/6fxvw-7t649	CC-BY-4.0
P1	Open		2026-02-28	Hugging Face		CC-BY-4.0

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Hugging Face (huggingface.co) is an American company specializing in artificial intelligence and machine learning tools. It offers an open-source platform that enables users to build, train, and deploy machine learning models across various modalities, including text, images, and audio. Hugging Face is dedicated to the FAIR principles, contributing to a more open, collaborative, and efficient AI research community.

Methods or software needed to access and use data:

No special resources are required to access the data. However, running a language model for fine-tuning on local hardware requires appropriate technical resources. The requirements vary depending on the model size (e.g. 7B, 13B, 70B parameters) and type of use (e.g. inference, fine tuning). Medium-sized models with 13B parameters require at least 32-64 GB RAM, a graphics card (GPU) with around 20 GB VRAM and sufficiently fast storage space (ideally SSDs).

Long-term preservation and deletion of data:

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	Members of the scientific community

V Legal and Ethical Aspects

V.1 Legal aspects	<p>Personal data:</p> <p>In the project, we will process personal data. Wherever personal data is processed, we will ensure compliance with data protection laws, by gaining informed consent for processing personal data, and by anonymisation of personal data for preservation and/or sharing.</p> <p>Nevertheless, the data included in this specific track of the project, is completely synthetic data. There is no personal or sensitive information in this dataset.</p> <p>Intellectual property rights and ownership:</p> <p>Reinhard Grabler will be the owner of the data generated. Nevertheless, we do not plan to impose any restrictions on the re-use of data generated and published during this project. If using the dataset, it should be cited accordingly following the recommendations of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).</p>
V.2 Ethical aspects	<p>Ethical issues:</p> <p>Ethical issues in the project have been identified and discussed with the Research Ethics Coordinator at TU Wien (www.tuwien.at/research-ethics). They are described in detail in separate documents. The research plan of the project was reviewed by the TU Wien Research Ethics Committee.</p>